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OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS FROM THE WESTERN BALKANS

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Introduction: Overweight and obesity are linked to an increased risk for developing noncommunicable diseases, which are the primary causes of mortality on a global scale. It is concerning that the occurrence of overweight individuals among university students globally ranges up to 40%, posing a significant public health challenge. To date, there has been limited research conducted on the prevalence and associated factors of overweight and obesity specifically among medical students in the Western Balkans region, encompassing Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Serbia. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of overweight and obesity among medical students from the Western Balkans and explore potential associations with demographic, socioeconomic, and health-related behavioural factors.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving the participation of 2452 students from 14 medical faculties across the five countries in the Western Balkan region in a period from November 2019 to February 2020. An online survey questionnaire was used as a research instrument.

Results: The findings of the study unveiled that among medical students in the Western Balkans, the prevalence of overweight was 12%, while obesity stood at 2.3%. Notably, being male and being a smoker were identified as significant positive predictors of overweight and obesity. Conversely, engaging in up to one hour of physical activity per day and undergoing preventive check-ups annually or as part of routine dormitory check-ups were associated with decreased odds of being overweight or obese.

Conclusions: Addressing these concerns necessitates the development of targeted public health educational initiatives that can effectively influence students and promote the adoption of healthy lifestyle habits. By doing so, efforts can be made to reduce the prevalence of overweight and obesity within the student population, consequently lowering the risk of noncommunicable diseases and enhancing overall population health.

Keywords: overweight and obesity, medical students, young adults, public health, Western Balkans